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Language and Culture.

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ABSTRACT:

This article discusses the relationship between language and culture. When talking about the interaction between language and culture, it is necessary to dwell in detail on the concept of "culture". There are many attempts to interpret this concept. Language and culture are interrelated concepts. And we will get acquainted with them in the following article.

KEY WORDS:

Language, thought, culture, popular culture, linguistic culture, anthropological research, characteristic, semiotic approach.

It can be seen that the concepts of language and culture are interdependent. But first, let's focus on the concept of language.

1. Each natural language reflects a certain way of perceiving and organizing (conceptualizing) the world. The essences expressed in it are embodied in some unified system of views, in a specific public philosophy, such a philosophy is defined as a mandatory rule for speakers of this language...

2. The language-specific way of conceptualizing reality (worldview) is partly universal and partly nationally specific, and speakers of different languages can see the world slightly differently, through the prism of their own language.

3. On the other hand, it is also "simplistic" because it is based on many important details of the scientific world view. In most cases, they are as complex and interesting as the scientific imagination.

G.V. According to Kolshansky, the search for a systematizing basis in the content organization of the language led linguists to the semantic analysis of the language. This approach to language implies a systematic view of the meaning of words. We are talking about the style of the semantic field. Semantic field usually refers to words and phrases grouped around a concept (sometimes - an idea). Such elements of the text assume that "semantic primitives" of words and idioms operate. is governed by its own internal laws and realizes its own "worldview" that is unlike any other similar phenomenon in the history of different languages and the same language. Even when different languages are siblings, differences in the way the world is perceived and conceptualized through language can be significant. In other words, worldviews in different

languages can have their own characteristics. In the linguistic landscape of the world, the ethnic mentality is actualized in the "basic" cultural concepts verbalized in symbolic images that reflect the mental image of the speakers of this language about the surrounding world.

Words expressing the same concept in different languages can differ according to their semantic capacity and cover different fragments of reality. The pieces of the mosaic that present the world view can be differentiated in different languages depending on the amount of conceptual material obtained as a result of the perception of the surrounding world in the human brain.

According to S.T. Ter-Minasova, the methods and forms of perception, as well as the formation of concepts, in turn depend on the socio-cultural and natural characteristics of the life of this speech community. Differences in thinking through language are manifested precisely in the perception of excess or lack of forms of expression of the same concept.

Y.D. Apresyan describes the current state of the issue of the "simple" image of the world in language and notes that such research is going in two main directions.

1. On the other hand, linguistic and general cultural consciousness "stereotypes" specific aspects of this ethnos are investigated. The author calls them specific linguistic and cultural isoglosses and isoglosses. These are the typical aspects of the heart, desire, fate, past, will and so on. On the other hand, the author notes, these are specific connotations of non-specific aspects (for example, symbols represented by colors in different cultures).

2. At the same time, "research on the search for and reconstruction of a pre-scientific integrated view of the world characteristic of language, albeit "simple", is being enriched. That is, "dialect in general" is being studied. In the opinion of the author, in this place, in the consideration of national identity, "the main attention is focused on the overall picture of this world in the language".

When talking about the interaction between language and culture, it is necessary to dwell in detail on the concept of "culture". There are many attempts to interpret this concept. For example:

G.V. Yelizarova includes the concept of "culture" among axiomatic concepts that seem intuitively transparent. However, it is extremely difficult to define such a complex concept. There are also definitions of culture that seek to cover all aspects of the concept without focusing on one aspect, such as "Culture is how we live here." Regarding the definition of culture the initial approach is based on the assumption that culture is a homogeneous state characteristic of all

societies. Differences in society are interpreted not as differences in their essence and content, but as differences in the same situation - the level of development of culture. Progress from savagery to civilization served as a yardstick.

The more signs of civilization a society has at its disposal, the more culturally advanced it is considered to be. We find the most vivid expression of this approach to the understanding of culture in the works of E. Taylor. His more widespread definition of culture expresses culture as a whole complex phenomenon that includes knowledge, beliefs, arts, morals, laws, customs and any other characteristics and habits that a person acquires as a member of a society. But it is difficult to agree with such a point of view: civilization and culture are very different concepts. One case cannot be evaluated by another case, because both these concepts refer to cases with different meanings.

At the end of the 19th century, with the beginning of the anthropological research of F. Boas, the term "culture" began to be applied to different societies. Such a modification of attitudes towards culture is very important in terms of the importance of language. Since then, language and culture are considered inextricably linked.

A. Vejbitskaya cites a particularly effective definition of culture proposed by Clifford Hertz. It says that culture is a historically formed pattern of essences embodied in symbols. It is an inherited system of ideas by which people communicate with each other and their knowledge of life and rules of life are recorded and developed based on these ideas.

E. Sepir defined culture as something that is the basis for the work and thinking of this society. The social approach to the definition of culture is based on the consideration of this state as a completely different state from nature, biological and physiological aspects that are not limited to a single individual, but are characteristic of a group of people who communicate.

A cognitive approach to the definition of culture is that as culture is acquired by an individual, mental realities, structures and processes can be considered in terms of This approach to the concept of culture pays special attention to culture as a process of knowledge and cognition and is called cognitive (V. Goodenough). The semiotic approach is based on the understanding of culture, first of all, as a system of signs that can be used as a means of communication (K. Lévi-Strauss). But none of the given definitions can be considered complete, because they reveal only one aspect of the multifaceted aspects of culture, they are limited to the "approach" to culture and do not consider it as a whole.

M.K.Mamardashvili and A.M.Pyatigorsky note that "culture is a phenomenon that introduces the automatism of objectively oriented thinking." E. Sepir writes: "There is no doubt that language plays a major role in the accumulation of culture and its historical inheritance. This applies equally to the highest levels of culture and its simplest forms. Most of the cultural fund of the simplest society is more or less clearly preserved in the form of a fixed language" The use of the term "simplest culture" may raise questions. We believe that all kinds of cultures will work, but there will never be the "simplest" or "advanced" cultures. According to Z.K.Tarlanov, "Language is not a simple form of communication and a simple tool, it is a completely independent world, whose laws and rules are essentially expressed through language, but the social psychology of language speakers and their It is closely related to the type and content of the culture it creates. Interpreting the relationship between language and culture is an extremely complex task. Language, thought, culture - these are phenomena that are always in motion, changing. In order to study them, it is necessary to stop them, but it will no longer be the same "language", "thought", "culture", or rather, they will not be themselves: they are o remains motionless, separated from each other. It is impossible to determine which was the primary one, but it is true that there is no ethnos without language, and the death of language means the destruction of both ethnos and culture. Thus, language, thought, and culture are so closely intertwined that in practice they form a three-component whole that none of these components can function (and therefore function) without the other two components. All of them interact with the surrounding world, reflect it and shape it at the same time. In doing so, they create phenomena called worldscapes.

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